

A STUDY OF TRANSVERSE CRACK FORMATION IN FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES BY GROWTH OF FIBER-MATRIX DEBONDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies a likely mechanism for formation of a macro-sized transverse crack consisting of growth and link-up of fiber-matrix debond cracks in a unidirectional composite loaded in transverse tension. The model used for this purpose is an embedded cell within a homogeneous composite. The cell has a fiber surrounded by six fibers in a hexagonal pattern. By analyzing the debonding of the central fiber, it is found that once initiated, the debond crack grows in mixed mode along the interface initially unstably and then stably. The analysis also shows that the driving force of a potential kinked crack emanating from debond tip increases and reaches its highest value before a physically relevant contact zone develops at the debond tip. The results suggest that the kinking of the debond crack out of interface and its growth towards neighboring fibers is nearly in pure mode I. Once the kinked crack approaches a neighboring fiber, it induces a high radial tensile stress in the neighboring fiber, causing a possible debonding of that fiber. This debonding followed by kinking out of the interface eventually leads to the formation of a macro-sized transverse crack.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the importance of the first matrix cracks in affecting subsequent damage in fiber-reinforced composite materials, a great deal of research has been devoted to understanding the formation of these cracks. Under transverse tension the observations reported by Gamstedt and Sjogren [1] suggest that fiber-matrix debonding occurs first followed by interconnection of the debond cracks into a continuous transverse crack. The initiation of debonding has been studied by Asp et al [2] by an energy based criterion. Once the debond cracks form as discrete entities, they can grow and link up to form a transverse crack. The present study is aimed at understanding the mechanisms involved in this growth and link-up process.

Fiber/matrix interfacial debond growth under transverse tension has been investigated extensively through single-fiber composite model [3-7] due to its simplicity. However, it is clear that a single-fiber composite is not representative of real composites where the stress field near any debonding fiber is significantly affected by the presence of surrounding fibers. It is not until recently that this issue has been addressed by a two-fiber model [8] and a composite model [9]. As to the kinking of a debond crack as well as the link-up process of neighboring debonds in a composite, the current understanding is still limited. Martyniuk et al [10] conducted a 3D in-situ observation of a single fiber composite and found that the kink-out of debond crack only occurs at the free surface and that the angle at which the kink-out begins is consistent with the numerical findings by Paris et al [11], i.e., between 60° and 70° of half debond angle when the energy release rate (ERR) of the kinked crack is highest. Several other studies [12, 13] tried to explain transverse crack formation via formation of a band of debonded fibers using various numerical techniques. However, the link-up process of the debond cracks is missing in

these models.

As an attempt to advance toward full clarification of the mechanism of macro-sized transverse crack formation, a numerical model is adopted here in which the growth and possible kink-out of a debond crack can be studied in the presence of surrounding fibers. The fiber clustering is represented by a set of six fibers arranged in a hexagonal pattern around a debonding fiber. The crack growth is studied by calculating the energy release rate (ERR), which is obtained through the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) using the Finite Element (FE) software ANSYS [14].

2 FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACIAL DEBOND GROWTH

Details of FE model adopted to investigate the fiber/matrix interfacial debond growth are shown in Fig 1. Due to the symmetry, only half of the composite is modelled. The initially debonded fiber is placed at the center of the model. The debond crack is placed on one side of the fiber surface with its mid-point normal aligned with the transverse loading direction. The debond has two tips and is assumed to propagate symmetrically with respect to the symmetric line, as shown in Fig 1. The debond crack size is quantified by the angle θ , as indicated in Fig 1. The debonded fiber is surrounded by six intact fibers in hexagonal pattern and the seven-fiber assembly within a circular matrix region is embedded in the homogenized composite. The distance between central fiber and nearby fibers ID is varied in order to investigate the effects of inter-fiber spacing on debond growth. The fiber radius $r_f = 4 \mu\text{m}$ and the radius of circular matrix region RMO is chosen such that the fiber volume fraction (denoted V_f) within this region equals the global fiber volume fraction of the composite. The half-height and width of the model are chosen as $H=20RMO$ and $W=40RMO$, respectively, beyond which the calculated ERR of the debond crack is not affected by the size of the model.

As shown in Fig 1, the x-displacement is applied uniformly to the right edge ($x = W$) of the model, while it is constrained on the left edge, to induce the strain $\epsilon_x = 0.5\%$. 2-D quadratic plane strain elements with pure Lagrange multipliers on normal and tangential contact were generated on the debond surface to model contact behavior with minimal interpenetration.

Figure 1: Illustration of fiber/matrix interfacial debonding model

In the present study, carbon fiber epoxy material with fiber volume fraction $V_f=0.6$ are considered. The elastic material properties for each constituent are displayed in Table 1. Two different inter-fiber spacing were investigated: $ID_n (ID/r_f) = 0.15$ and $ID_n=0.35$. The ERR results for two cases subjected to pure mechanical loading $\epsilon_x = 0.5\%$ are shown in Fig 2. It should be noted that although we only

consider pure mechanical loading in the present study, a separate study [9] by the current authors found that the presence of thermal stress would only reduce the ERR of debond without altering the overall trend significantly. As a result, the trend discussed in the following should also be valid for thermo-mechanical loading. As displayed in Fig 2, for both inter-fiber spacing cases, debond growth is mixed-mode. Both mode I ERR component (G_I) and mode II ERR component (G_{II}) increase first and then decrease with increasing debond angle θ , which results in the similar trend for total ERR G_T ($G_T = G_I + G_{II}$). The present trend of ERR indicates an initial unstable debond growth followed by stable growth. When debond grows to an angle $\theta \approx 70^\circ$, a finite contact zone is detected between two debond surface and G_I diminishes. This angle is of interest as Martyniuk et al [10] discovered that debond stops growing when a physically relevant contact zone developed between two debond surfaces in a single fiber composite test. As a result, it's reasonable to assume that the debond growth is governed by mode I ERR and the maximum angle the debond could grow in the current case is $\theta \approx 70^\circ$.

Material	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{23}
CF	500	30	0.2	20	0.45
Epoxy	3.5	3.5	0.4	1.25	0.4
CF/EP ($V_f=0.6$)	301.4	11.04	0.27	4.06	0.54

Table 1: Elastic properties of constituents

Figure 2: ERR of debond subjected to pure mechanical loading ($\epsilon_x = 0.5\%$)

3 CRACK KINKING FROM FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACE

In the previous section we have discussed the debond growth along fiber/matrix interface. However, debonds by itself would not form a macro-sized transverse crack. As found by numerous experimental studies, for example [1, 15], the macro-sized transverse crack is formed by the coalesce

of individual debonds through matrix cracking. As a result, in this section, we will discuss the potential debond crack kinking towards matrix from fiber/matrix interface.

Figure 3 illustrates the FE model used to investigate the potential debond crack kinking. The geometry is the same as in Fig 1. For each debond angle θ , a kinked crack of length $L=0.04 r_f$ is assumed to emanate from debond tip and grow towards matrix in an angle θ' with respect to the horizontal axis of the model. The kinking angle θ' is determined based on the maximum energy release rate criteria: i.e. crack is assumed to kink out of interface in a direction that maximizes the ERR of kinked crack. For a crack length smaller than $L=0.04r_f$ or slightly larger than this value, it's found that (not reported here) although the predicted ERR values of kinked crack varied slightly depending on the crack length, the predicted kinking angle does not alter significantly. As a result, $L=0.04 r_f$ is adopted in the present study to investigate the crack kinking.

Figure 3: Illustration of crack kinking model

Figures 4 and 5 display the obtained ERR for the kinked crack and the debond for two different inter-fiber spacing cases. For both cases, the potential kinking angle θ' is found to be between $75^\circ \sim 80^\circ$ for all the debond angles studied. From Figs 4 and 5 it is hard to make any assessments based on the exact values of ERR due to lack of information about the critical ERR value for fiber/matrix interface as well as matrix material. However, the observed trend of ERR for both kinked crack and debond is very interesting and could very well give us an indication about the potential kinking of the debond.

Figure 4: Comparison of ERR between kinked crack and debond for $IDn=0.15$

Figure 5: Comparison of ERR between kinked crack and debond for $IDn=0.35$

As shown in Fig 4, although we predict the crack kinking based on the maximum energy release rate criterion, the obtained ERR of kinked crack indicates that debond tends to kink out of interface in pure mode I. This trend has also been found by other studies [16, 17]. From Figs 4 and 5 it is found that the ERR of kinked crack reaches its maximum value at $\theta \approx 30^\circ$ for $IDn=0.15$ and $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ for $IDn=0.35$, which suggests that the angle when the maximum ERR of kinked crack occurs increases with increasing inter-fiber spacing. This is consistent with the results obtained by Paris et al [11] as they found the angle for maximum ERR of kinked crack is between 60° and 70° of half debond angle for a single fiber composite and a single fiber composite could be considered, in the present case, as the scenario when inter-fiber space is sufficiently large so that there is no influence from neighboring

fibers.

A closer look at Figs 4 and 5 shows that the maximum ERR of kinked crack occurs when the mode I component of debond is decreasing. The difference of mode I ERR between kinked crack and debond increasing as debond angle increases until debond closes. This could be demonstrated better in Fig 6. As displayed in Fig 6, the difference of mode I ERR between kinked crack and debond increases significantly when the ERR of kinked crack reaches the maximum value and maintains at a relatively large margin until debond tip close ($\theta \approx 70^\circ$). Given the importance of mode I ERR component in debond growth, it is reasonable to suggest that crack kinking would most likely to occur when the debond angles is between one that maximize the ERR of kinked crack (varied with inter-fiber spacing) and the one when a physically relevant contact zone developed at the debond tip.

Figure 6: Difference of mode I ERR between kinked crack and debond

4 MATRIX CRACK PROPAGATION

Once a debond crack kinks out of the interface, the propagation of the kinked crack towards neighboring fibers is simulated based on a procedure similar to the previous determination of the kinked crack: once the original kinked crack (denoted as “first kink”) is determined, the direction of the following kinked crack propagation is based on the maximum energy release rate criterion, the same procedure continues until kinked crack propagates near neighboring fibers. In the present study, we assume debond to kink out of interface when the ERR of the kinked crack is the maximum and study three different step of propagation of matrix crack including first kink. Two different inter-fiber spacing cases are considered. The predicted kinked crack path towards neighboring Fiber #1 is shown in Fig 7. Similar to the discussion in section 3, kinked crack tends to propagate towards neighboring fiber in pure mode I. It is found that the crack propagation process is stable as ERR of kinked crack decreases as crack propagates. This is a different result compared to the ones obtained using single fiber composite model [11], which highlights the importance of neighboring fibers’ influence. As shown in Fig 7, when the kinked crack approaches the neighboring fiber, instead of propagating directly towards it, it diverts and tends to reach the neighboring fiber at a certain angle as a reflection of the complex stress field near neighboring fiber.

Figure 8 display the radial stress distribution along the interface of Fiber #1 during kinked crack propagation (θ_n is indicated in Fig 3 and is positive clock-wise along Fiber #1). As shown in Fig 8, when the kinked crack gets closer to Fiber #1 (third kink) as indicated in Fig 7, a small region close to kinked crack tip with very high radial tensile stress developed in Fiber #1, this localized high radial

tensile stress, if reaching the critical value to break the bonds of fiber/matrix interface, will initiate fiber/matrix debonding process in Fiber#1, and similar fiber/matrix debonding process as well as debond kinking process would also occur in Fiber#1 if the correct conditions are met. The repeat of the whole process will eventually lead to the formation of macro-sized transverse crack.

For the case $ID_n=0.15$, similar kinked crack propagation process is found as shown in Fig 9. However, based on the results displayed in Figs 2 and 6, it is clear that the driving force for debond growth as well as debond kinking is higher for larger inter-fiber spacing which indicates that for the macro-sized crack formation mechanism discussed in the present paper, i.e single fiber/matrix debond growth, kinking and kinked crack propagation leading to the further debonding of neighboring fiber, it is more likely to occur when the distances between nearby fibers are relatively large. An ongoing work is to investigate the preferred mechanism for transverse crack formation when inter-fiber spacings are relatively small.

Figure 7: Predicted matrix crack and radial stress along Fiber#1 interface. ($ID_n=0.35, \theta=40^\circ$)

Figure 8: Radial stress distribution along interface for Fiber#1

Figure 9: Predicted matrix crack and radial stress along Fiber#1 interface. (IDn=0.15, $\theta=30^\circ$)

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have investigated a likely mechanism for macro-sized transverse crack formation by a model that accounts for the presence of fiber clusters in a composite. Based on the obtained results, following conclusions could be made:

1. Once the initial fiber/matrix interfacial debond is formed, it will grow along the interface first in mixed-mode. The initial debond growth has been found to be unstable and becoming stable with further growth. The debond growth is most likely governed by mode I ERR.
2. As the debond grows, the ERR of the potential kinked crack shows that at a certain angle (depending on the inter-fiber spacing), when the ERR reaches its maximum, the debond crack is likely to kink out rather than continuing along the interface. This occurs before a physically relevant contact zone develops at the debond tip, making further growth of the debond crack along the interface less likely.
3. The kinking out of the debond crack from the interface is in pure mode I and further propagation towards a neighboring fiber is also in pure mode I.
4. As the kinked crack approaches a neighboring fiber, a localized region with very high radial tensile stress develops on the fiber, leading to the possible initiation of debonding of the fiber from the matrix. The whole process (including debond growth, kinking and propagation) continues and results in the formation of a macro-sized transverse crack. This crack formation process is found to be more likely to occur when the inter-fiber spacing is relatively large.

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